

1 **Introducing Fiji and ICY image processing techniques in ichnological research as a**
2 **tool for sedimentary basin analysis**

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11

12 **Abstract**

13 In recent years, image treatment has been appraised as a very powerful tool to
14 facilitate ichnological analysis, especially in marine cores of modern sediments,
15 supporting the determination of certain ichnological features. However, it is still a new
16 approach and detailed research is necessary to encounter a faster and more efficient
17 method. The present study focuses on two image processing techniques, Fiji and ICY,
18 and their comparison with a refined version of the well-established high-resolution image
19 treatment. Strengths and weaknesses of the methodologies for the determination of three
20 main features were explored: i) visibility of trace fossils; ii) quantification of the
21 percentage of bioturbated surface, and iii) penetration depth estimation. Refined high-
22 resolution image treatment gives the best results for enhanced visibility of trace fossils,
23 whereas Fiji is found to be a sound and rapid option. One disadvantage shared by Fiji and
24 ICY is the binary character of the produced images, which may impede later
25 ichnotaxonomical differentiation. Both Fiji and ICY (+ Fiji) are rapid alternatives for
26 quantifying the bulk amount of bioturbated surface. The Magic Wand Method (+
27 RefineEdge), based on high-resolution image treatment, provides good results regardless
28 of the contrast of the images, and it additionally allows for a more detailed quantification.
29 The semi-automatic character of ICY favors quick estimation of penetration depth and

30 facilitates differentiation between distinct tracemaker communities, based on a rapid
31 quantification of pixel values. Thus, Fiji and ICY methods offer good results and are
32 much less time-consuming than high-resolution image treatment. They are proposed as
33 faster alternatives for the estimation of ichnological features, especially useful at the
34 beginning stages of research, when a large number of samples must be analyzed.

35

36 *Keywords:* Image treatment methods, high-resolution images, degree of bioturbation,
37 penetration depth, basin research.

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40 The study of trace fossils has been documented as a very useful tool in several
41 Earth Sciences disciplines including palaeontology, sedimentology, marine geology or
42 palaeoceanography, and proven key in sedimentary basin research(e.g., Buatois and
43 Mángano, 2011; Knaust and Bromley, 2012). Trace fossils record the behavior of
44 tracemakers in response to the environment, providing valuable information regarding
45 paleoenvironmental conditions. Ecological and depositional parameters affecting the
46 marine realm (i.e., oxygenation, nutrients, hydrodynamic energy, rate of sedimentation,
47 etc.) can be addressed through a detailed ichnological analysis. Thus, ichnology is a
48 valuable proxy for approaching marine processes or deposits. Most of these ichnological
49 advances have entailed the application of two main paradigms: the ichnofabric approach
50 (McIlroy, 2004; Buatois and Mángano, 2011; Ekdale et al., 2012) and the ichnofacies
51 model (Buatois and Mángano, 2011; MacEachern et al., 2012), both based on a detailed
52 characterization of ichnological properties (i.e., trace fossil assemblage, degree of
53 bioturbation, among others). Occasionally, these properties are difficult to determine due
54 to a poor visibility of the trace fossils in the studied samples. Against this background, in
55 recent years, high-resolution image treatment has been successfully applied for the
56 ichnological analysis of marine cores from modern deposits, proving useful for
57 ichnofabric characterization and ichnofacies differentiation (see Dorador and Rodríguez-
58 Tovar, 2018 for a recent review of the methodology).

59 Image treatment allows for a better visualization of biogenic structures, thereby
60 making it easier to identify ichnological properties such as morphology, degree of
61 bioturbation or penetration depth, which are of special relevance in applied ichnology
62 (e.g., Bednarz and McIlroy, 2009; Dorador et al., 2014a, b; Rodríguez-Tovar and
63 Dorador, 2014, 2015; Timmer et al., 2016, among others). The use of high-resolution
64 image treatment also contributes to studies surrounding paleoenvironmental

65 developments (e.g., Rodríguez-Tovar and Dorador, 2014; Rodríguez-Tovar et al., 2015a,
66 b; Dorador and Rodríguez-Tovar, 2016a; Dorador et al., 2016) and provides information
67 for sedimentary basin research (e.g., Alonso et al., 2016; Dorador and Rodríguez-Tovar,
68 2016b; Takashimizu et al., 2016), supported by the ichnological approach. So far, these
69 techniques have been mainly applied on marine cores from modern deposits. However,
70 Dorador and Rodríguez-Tovar (2018) recently showed that image treatment might be an
71 adequate method for analyzing lithified cores and rock samples. While its usefulness has
72 been clearly demonstrated, the application of high-resolution image treatment takes time,
73 a plain fact that encourages further exploration of this approach to find the most efficient
74 and less time-consuming methods. With this goal in mind, two software packages widely
75 used in biological and medical research were selected to test and compare their
76 performance: Fiji, as an extension of the ImageJ software; and ICY software.

77 Fiji software (Schindelin et al., 2012) is an extension of the well-known open-
78 source software ImageJ, commonly but not exclusively applied in biological and medical
79 studies (Schneider et al., 2012 and references therein), and less frequently in geological
80 research (e.g., Grove and Jerran, 2011; Goldstein et al., 2017). ImageJ has been
81 punctually used in ichnological analysis to enhance visibility of certain image attributes,
82 to estimate bioturbated surface and to make shape/length measurements (Francus, 2001;
83 Nicolo et al., 2010; Lauridsen et al., 2011; Curth et al., 2014). Fiji has already been
84 applied in neo-ichnological analysis for format conversion in reconstructed volumes
85 obtained by computed tomography of invertebrate burrow systems (Hale et al., 2015),
86 and recently to estimate the degree of bioturbation (Miguez-Salas and Rodríguez-Tovar,
87 2019). This method holds great potential for ichnological studies because its toolbox
88 features diverse tools and filters for the measurement of specific paleontological

89 parameters (i.e., shape/length of bones; Iepure et al., 2012; Jarrett, 2016; O'Connor et al.,
90 2018).

91 Whereas ICY software has been applied in cell biology studies for tracking,
92 extracting or actively delimiting particles/cells (e.g., de Chaumont et al., 2011; Meijering
93 et al., 2012; Montagnac et al., 2013), it has not been previously applied to geological
94 research. The present research marks the first documented testing of its usefulness in the
95 realm of ichnological aspects.

96 The aim of this paper is to examine two image processing techniques, Fiji and
97 ICY, to approach a fast and useful method for the early research stages of ichnological
98 studies in which numerous samples and images are examined. Then, the results obtained
99 with the application of these two techniques are compared with a slightly modified
100 version of a previously applied high-resolution image treatment (recent review in Dorador
101 and Rodríguez-Tovar, 2018). In light of their comparison, the strengths and weaknesses
102 of each procedure are characterized, outlining the most efficient approach for applied
103 ichnology in sedimentary basin research.

104

105 **2. Methods and materials**

106

107 Two image treatment methods applied to ichnology—Fiji and ICY— plus the
108 refined version of high-resolution image treatment were assessed for their usefulness in
109 ichnological analysis. The focus was on: (1) enhanced trace fossil visualization; (2)
110 quantification of bioturbated surface corresponding to discrete trace fossils; and (3)
111 minimum penetration depth.

112

113 **2.1. Fiji**

114

115 Fiji software offers a wide range of plugins for enhancing image visibility, similar
116 to the image adjustments of Adobe Photoshop (e.g., *brightness, hue, saturation, levels*).
117 For the purposes of this study, to provide quick image visibility improvement, the
118 Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) method was selected (Fig.
119 1A). This provides better visibility of ichnological features in a short time through the
120 local contrast of an image based on modification of two main parameters: i) block size,
121 controlling the size of the local region around a pixel for which the histogram is equalized;
122 and ii) histogram bins, defining the number of bins used for histogram equalization, which
123 should be smaller than the number of pixels in a block.

124 For the quantification of bioturbated surface, after applying CLAHE, the obtained
125 image must be converted to an 8-bit grayscale image. Then, the threshold has to be
126 defined to establish a differentiation range for black and white by means of the *Image*
127 menu. The determination of this parameter is supported by a preview screen, where the
128 potential image is observed, and the value can be modified to obtain a more appropriate
129 bioturbated differentiation (black pixels were assigned to bioturbation). The enhanced
130 black and white binary image can be used to quantify the amount of bioturbated surface
131 (Fig. 1B left). The Fiji process menu offers a wide range of easy-to-use binary tools and
132 filters (e.g., dilate, erode, fill holes and skeletonize, among others). After testing, the
133 following ones were selected as the most suitable for ichnological analysis: a) Erode: it
134 removes erratic black pixels from the edges of bioturbation, proving extremely useful to
135 delete minor compounds of black pixels that do not correspond to trace fossils, and
136 thereby more precisely discern the shape of the burrows; b) Fill holes: it fills white pixels
137 located inside the trace fossils that are surrounded by black ones; and c)
138 Minimum/Maximum filters: they perform binary erosion by replacing each pixel in the
139 image with the smallest/largest pixel value in that pixel's neighborhood, helping one to

140 remove small black pixels that conform background noise (Fig. 1B right). All these tools
141 and filters present a preview option, which makes it easy, quick and intuitive to select the
142 size of the neighborhood.

143 Finally, manual corrections can be conducted using eraser or painting tools,
144 controlling that all the selected pixels belong to trace fossils. Afterwards, output
145 measurement results are quickly obtained with the Fiji analyze menu, whose program
146 measures the percentage of black pixels, hence offering a quantification of the bioturbated
147 surface.

148

149 **2.2. ICY**

150

151 ICY software uses an adaptive histogram equalization to enhance trace fossil
152 visibility (Fig. 2A). This plugin controls parameters similar to Fiji's, but through a
153 distinctive automatic procedure, giving different results.

154 When it is used to quantify bioturbated surface, ICY software can extract part of
155 the image according to pixel values via a thresholding menu. The pixel selection can be
156 done through manual adjustment, where threshold values are defined to derive a binary
157 image (Fig. 2B left). The selection may also be obtained automatically using the K-Means
158 tool, whose algorithm calculates the threshold value after defining the number of "classes"
159 (i.e., areas in the histogram) to be differentiated (value 2 for binary images). In the case
160 of abundant background noise, a high threshold value should be chosen to ensure that
161 bioturbation is well delimited and assigned to white pixels (Fig. 2B left). The derived
162 image can then be exported and inverted by Fiji. A final filtering treatment and estimation
163 of bioturbated surface should be conducted using Fiji, repeating the process, to arrive at
164 improved yet rapid results (Fig. 2B right).

165 Finally, the Intensity Profile plugin was used here to characterize the penetration
166 depth of trace fossils with passive filling (i.e., material that filled a burrow by physical
167 sedimentation after its occupant departed; Bromley, 1990). This plugin calculates the
168 intensity value of each pixel (obtaining three values per pixel, one for each channel) along
169 a particular Region Of Interest (ROI). The values are plotted on intensity profile graphics
170 from a given ROI (vertical line along the core), after which they must be manually
171 checked and filtered to identify potential mistakes. The final graphs of intensity values
172 along the ROI are used to compare intensity values from the infilling material with those
173 from the host sediment. Similar values allow one to recognize the colonization horizon
174 and then estimate the penetration depth of passively filled trace fossils from this horizon.
175

176 ***2.3. High-resolution image treatment***

177

178 The tested high-resolution image treatment for enhancing trace fossil visualization
179 is based on the method defined by Dorador et al. (2014). This technique modifies some
180 image adjustments (i.e., *levels*, *brightness* and *vibrance*) to increase the contrast between
181 the host sediment and the infilling material. It was initially proposed in sediment core
182 research, and later it was tested in rock samples after minor modification (see Dorador
183 and Rodríguez-Tovar, 2018, for a review).

184 To characterize the percentage of bioturbated surface, Dorador et al. (2014b)
185 presented a package consisting of three selection tools: Similar Pixel Selection Method
186 (SPSM), Magic Wand Method (MWM) and Color Range Selection Method (CRSM). In
187 the present study, to further enhance quantification, selections obtained from each of the
188 above methods (Fig. 3B left) were slightly modified using a novel resource called
189 RefineEdge (Fig. 3B right). It enables one to refine the selected area, corresponding to
190 the biogenic structure, by modifying five parameters (*Radius*, *Smooth*, *Feather*, *Contrast*

191 and *Shift Edge*), giving rise to a better characterization of the discrete trace fossil. The
192 *Radius* parameter controls the size of the border in which refinement is applied. Once the
193 size is defined, *Smooth*, *Feather* and *Contrast* are modified. *Smooth* makes it possible to
194 remove hills and valleys, smoothing the border; *Feather* smudges the boundary between
195 the selected area and surrounding pixels; and *Contrast* modifies transitions along the
196 border. Finally, borders can be moved inward or outward by means of the *Shift Edge*
197 parameter, controlling the final selected area.

198 Penetration depth is determined by high-resolution digital image treatment
199 following quantitative pixel analysis, as was proposed by Dorador and Rodríguez-Tovar
200 (2014). Host sediment pixels and those from the infilling material of trace fossils are
201 quantified and plotted, and the comparison between pixel values allows the penetration
202 depth to be evaluated (Dorador and Rodríguez-Tovar, 2014).

203

204 **2.4. Data set**

205 Numerous images from sediment cores and outcrops were considered in this
206 study. For core samples, the data set consisted of high-resolution images from IODP
207 Expedition 339, subjected to numerous ichnological studies during recent years (e.g.,
208 Rodríguez-Tovar and Dorador, 2014; Rodríguez-Tovar et al., 2015a, b; Dorador and
209 Rodríguez-Tovar, 2016a, 2018). Core images were from 1.5 m sections split lengthwise
210 and scanned (on the Section Half Imaging Logger) on board during the cruise (Expedition
211 339 Scientists, 2013a). Fifty-four of these core samples were selected, and 10-20 cm core
212 intervals were cropped from every core section in view of potentially interesting
213 ichnological content. Additionally, two core segments were selected from IODP Site
214 U1385 corresponding to core depths of 40.05 to 40.20 meters (U1385A-5H-CC) and 70.7
215 to 70.9 meters (U1385-8H-5A) to analyze the penetration depth. They are mainly

216 hemipelagic claystones, with no primary sedimentary structures, but many discrete trace
217 fossils over a mottled background (Expedition 339 Scientists, 2013b, Rodríguez-Tovar
218 and Dorador, 2014).

219 Several images of outcrop samples from the Cyprus carbonate contourite drift
220 succession (Petra Tou Rominou section; see Stow et al., 2002) and Moroccan Miocene
221 sandy contourite channels (Capella et al., 2017) were furthermore considered.
222 Ichnological studies of these rocks reveal informative examples of variable relationships
223 between trace fossils and host sediment. Before taking photographs (Canon ® PowerShot
224 SX420), outcrops were sprayed with water to improve trace fossil visibility. More than
225 100 images corresponding to several lithologies (chalk, calcilutites, calcarenites) were
226 treated to evaluate different cases (for chalk, see Miguez-Salas and Rodríguez-Tovar,
227 2019). Finally, based on the contrast between the trace fossils and the surrounded
228 material, three images were selected as illustrative and representative examples:
229 calcarenite (high contrast), chalk (medium contrast) and calcilutite (low contrast).

230

231 **3. Comparative analysis**

232

233 Comparison of the selected methods (i.e., Fiji, ICY and high-resolution image
234 treatment) served to highlight the strengths and weaknesses of each in improving the
235 visibility of trace fossils and quantification of bioturbated surface. In the case of high-
236 resolution image treatment and ICY, we were able to compare the penetration depth as
237 well.

238

239 ***3.1. Enhancing visibility of bioturbation***

240

241 The techniques were applied on outcrop images to increase the visibility of trace
242 fossils, and consequently facilitate ichnotaxonomical identification. For a detailed

243 comparison, three examples were selected based on the original contrast (high, medium
244 and low contrast) between trace fossils and the surrounding sediment (Fig. 4).

245 Application of the high-resolution image treatment served to enhance the
246 visualization of trace fossils in the three examples, being particularly successful in low
247 and medium contrast examples, where some ichnotaxa could not be identified in the
248 original image. Reliable identification and characterization of some *Chondrites* was only
249 possible after the treatment (Fig. 4).

250 The CLAHE methodology conducted with Fiji provides good results for medium
251 to low contrast samples, especially for highlighting *Thalassinoides* and *Planolites* (Fig.
252 4). However, differentiation of *Chondrites* is still difficult after treatment. In the case of
253 the high contrast example, visualization of traces such as *Chondrites* is aided by treatment
254 (Fig. 4).

255 Adaptive histogram equalization in ICY gives excellent results for the reddish
256 *Chondrites* of the high-contrast image (Fig. 4), although improvement in trace fossil
257 visualization is relatively low in those images with medium to low contrast between trace
258 fossils and surrounding sediment (Fig. 4).

259

260 ***3.2. Quantification of bioturbated surface corresponding to discrete trace fossils***

261

262 High-resolution image treatment entailed using the refined versions of Color
263 Range Selection Method (CRSM), Magic Wand Method (MWM) and Similar Pixels
264 Selection Method (SPSM) on high, medium and low contrast examples (Fig. 5). The three
265 techniques provided similar values for bioturbated surface corresponding to discrete trace
266 fossils in the high contrast example —from 9% to 12%— indicating a low degree of
267 bioturbation (BI = 2, according to bioturbation index of Taylor and Goldring, 1993).

268 These differences are higher in the medium contrast image, where quantification ranges

269 from 10% to 19%, although both values correspond to the same bioturbation index (BI =
270 2). Finally, application on the low contrast example gives more variable values, from 19%
271 to 47%; estimations obtained with CRSM and MWM represent a low index of
272 bioturbation (BI = 2), while that from SPSM corresponds to a higher index (BI = 3).

273 In conjunction with Fiji and ICY methods, the amount of bioturbated surface
274 corresponding to discrete trace fossils was calculated before and after filtering binary
275 images (Figs. 1, 2 and 5). Both techniques show similar results in the high contrast
276 outcrop image (15% and 16%) pertaining to a low bioturbation index (BI = 2). The results
277 obtained from medium (16% and 20%) and low (19% to 22%) contrast images are also
278 similar, corresponding, at any rate, to a low bioturbation index (BI = 2 for all). Filtering
279 was less complex in the case of binary images obtained with Fiji methodology. In the case
280 of ICY method, the filtering was especially difficult due to the assignment of some host
281 sediment areas as pixels belonging to trace fossils.

282

283 ***3.3. Penetration depth***

284

285 Penetration depth values were calculated, and then compared, using both the
286 quantitative pixel analysis proposed by Dorador and Rodríguez-Tovar (2014), and the
287 Intensity Profile plugin by ICY (IP-ICY). In both cases, images were previously treated
288 with high-resolution image treatment and Fiji (CLAHE), respectively, to improve trace
289 fossil visualization. As explained previously, we focus on passively filled trace fossils;
290 comparison between data (mean pixel values in case of the high-resolution image
291 treatment and intensity values in case of IP-ICY) from the infilling material with those of
292 the host sediment enabled us to approach the colonization horizon and then estimate the
293 penetration depth. Two core segments from IODP Site U1385 having different contrast
294 between the fill material of trace fossils and the surrounding sediments were studied: a

295 higher contrast image corresponding to U1385A-5H-CC, and a lower contrast image to
296 U1385A-8H-5A (Fig. 6).

297 In general, the results of the two methods were similar, but some noteworthy
298 differences should be pointed out (Fig. 6). For the higher contrast example, the high-
299 resolution image treatment improved visualization of three *Thalassinoides* cross-sections
300 and the quantitative pixel analysis allowed the identification of corresponding penetration
301 depths of 2.8, 3.6 and 9.8 cm (Fig. 6A left). The IP-ICY shows two intensity value
302 packages that can be linked to *Thalassinoides*; the first records penetration depths of 2.6,
303 3.5 and 5.5 cm, and the second shows lower intensity values, giving an estimated
304 penetration depth of 9.5 cm (Fig. 6A right). For the low contrast core interval, according
305 to quantitative pixel analysis, four *Thalassinoides* cross-sections showed penetration
306 depths of 1.8, 6.3 and 10.0 (in two cases) cm (Fig. 6B left). Using IP-ICY it is more
307 difficult to distinguish between the fill of trace fossils and the host sediment, although
308 four different intensity value packages might be associated with the four *Thalassinoides*
309 cross-sections, having penetration depths of 2, 9, 10 and 11 cm.

310

311 **4. Discussion**

312

313 This study confirms that image processing techniques facilitate trace fossil
314 analysis when applied to characterize particular ichnological features such as
315 ichnodiversity, quantification of bioturbation, and penetration depth. Our comparative
316 analysis furthermore served to evidence strengths and weaknesses of the three studied
317 methodologies (Table 1).

318 In terms of enhanced trace fossil visualization —facilitating trace fossil
319 differentiation and therefore ichnotaxonomical classification— the three methods provide
320 good results for high contrast images (Fig. 4). Results for mid and low contrast examples

321 show some differences depending on the applied method, with better results after
322 applying high-resolution image treatment and Fiji (CLAHE), and weaker visualization
323 after adaptive histogram by ICY. Given the rapid processing of Fiji, this option may be
324 seen as an alternative to the time-consuming high-resolution image treatment. This
325 approach is especially promising for preliminary analyses, since the outstanding results
326 on cores (Fig. 6) may be helpful when selecting the most appropriate core segments
327 during the initial stages of a research study. In sum, the Fiji quick treatment facilitates
328 decision-making in studies involving a great number of cores or outcrop samples. More
329 detailed analysis can be conducted later through the application of high-resolution image
330 treatment. Furthermore, whereas Fiji and ICY work with black and white binary images,
331 the fact that high-resolution image treatment allows one to apply different colors
332 according to the pixel values makes ichnotaxonomical classification easier.

333 All the applied methods quantify the abundance of bioturbation exclusively to
334 discrete trace fossils (having differentiated outlines and characteristic shapes), without
335 any evaluation of the biodeformational structures or bioturbated texture (undifferentiated
336 outlines with no definitive geometry, a mottled background). However, after
337 characterization of the presence/absence of a mottled background, quantification of the
338 bioturbated surface corresponding to discrete trace fossils is indeed of interest, bearing a
339 relationship with palaeoenvironmental conditions.

340 The overall comparison of the different methodologies tested indicates that all of
341 them provide good results for high contrast examples, ranging from 9% to 16% of
342 bioturbated surface (Fig. 5), which belong to a low degree of bioturbation ($BI = 2$) (Fig.
343 5). Results are similar for medium contrast images (10%–20%), belonging to the same
344 bioturbation index ($BI = 2$). At the opposite end, application on low contrast images
345 shows very substantial differences, from 19% to 47%, though most values are around

346 20% (the exception being SPSM + RefineEdge). Accordingly, and taking into account
347 that CRSM underestimates the amount of bioturbation, as some trace fossil pixels are not
348 selected, the most successful selection tool would be Magic Wand Method (+
349 RefineEdge), providing very realistic results in all the studied examples. Since MWM is
350 time-consuming, especially when working with small trace fossils (Dorador et al.,
351 2014b), Fiji stands as an attractive alternative for low contrast samples, and ICY (+ Fiji)
352 for medium contrast ones. For precise results both programs (Fiji and ICY) require
353 complex filtering; however, the results of initial automatic estimation without filters are
354 not very different from the final values (Figs. 1 and 2), meaning they lend themselves to
355 rapid initial appraisals. Finally, in high contrast images, any method can be applied—all
356 three offer realistic results about the bioturbated surface corresponding to discrete trace
357 fossils. Again, an important advantage of any high-resolution image treatment over Fiji
358 and ICY resides in the possibility to estimate the percentage of area occupied for each
359 ichnotaxon, the whole ichnocoenosis, or the complete ichnofabric (Rodríguez-Tovar and
360 Dorador, 2015). Fiji and ICY only allow for quantification of the whole bioturbated
361 surface as they work with binary images.

362 In terms of penetration depth, good results were obtained for the core examples
363 after either method, quantitative pixel analysis in the case of high-resolution image
364 treatment or the intensity values in the case of IP-ICY. Still, the most appropriate
365 procedure might be selected in light of the particular contrast of the images at hand. When
366 dealing with a higher contrast image, both methods show similar values for penetration,
367 supporting the obtained values; but the record of two intensity value packages with IP-
368 ICY might indicate two different communities of *Thalassinoides* tracemaker, which could
369 have paleoecological implications. For the low contrast core section, the scarce
370 differentiation between the values associated with the fill of trace fossils and those from

371 the host sediment in the IP-ICY analyses would impede a precise estimation, which can
372 be obtained with the quantitative pixel analysis. Nonetheless, as in the previous case, data
373 from IP-ICY allow discernment between two different communities of *Thalassinoides*
374 tracemaker coming from two distinct horizons of colonization. Although both methods
375 are valuable for estimating penetration depth, the semi-automatic character of IP-ICY
376 favors faster calculation. In short, IP-ICY is a promising tool for characterizing the
377 penetration depth of some trace fossils in a very rapid and intuitive way, especially for
378 high contrast images, facilitating even the differentiation between distinct horizons of
379 colonization. In any case, this approach must be supported by a precise ichnological
380 analysis to avoid misinterpretation of the obtained pixel values, as those determined by
381 reworking of biogenic structures (e.g., *Thalassinoides* reworked by other traces as
382 *Chondrites*).

383

384 ***4.1. The applied techniques: consequences for paleoenvironmental research***

385

386 Conducted research supports the usefulness of the image processing techniques
387 evaluated here when characterizing particular ichnological features: ichnodiversity,
388 quantification of bioturbation, and penetration depth. All these features are of major
389 interest in any ichnological study, and especially under the ichnofabric approach
390 (McIlroy, 2004; Buatois and Mángano, 2011; Ekdale et al., 2012) and the ichnofacies
391 model (Buatois and Mángano, 2011; MacEachern et al., 2012). Both these paradigms in
392 ichnological analysis have become consolidated as significant proxies to interpret
393 sedimentary environments (Knaust and Bromley, 2012), based on the characterization of
394 ecological and depositional conditions.

395 The ichnofabric approach has been successfully used as a tool in a range of Earth
396 Science disciplines, but particularly for paleoenvironmental research and sedimentary

397 basin analysis, and recently for reservoir characterization (McIlroy, 2004; Buatois and
398 Mángano, 2011; Ekdale et al., 2012). Detailed ichnofabric analysis calls for integrating
399 ichnofabric attributes, including ichnotaxa diversity, ichnological features (i.e.,
400 dimensions of ichnotaxa), amount of bioturbation, cross-cutting relationships, and/or
401 tiering structures (Taylor et al., 2003). Such ichnofabric attributes are controlled by
402 depositional and ecological conditions: grain size, nature of substrate, oxygenation,
403 nutrient levels, salinity, and sedimentation rate, among others, determined by particular
404 depositional processes (Taylor et al., 2003). On this basis, the applied image processing
405 techniques would facilitate ichnofabric characterization, hence environmental
406 interpretations.

407 Because the ichnofacies model looks into groups of trace fossils that reflect animal
408 responses (ethology) to paleoenvironmental conditions (Buatois and Mángano, 2011;
409 MacEachern et al., 2012), a detailed ichnofacies characterization proves essential for
410 paleoenvironmental analysis and sedimentary basin research. Means of improving
411 ichnotaxonomic analysis is important not only for the recognition and differentiation of
412 ichnofacies; it becomes fundamental when working with cores from modern marine
413 sediments showing a comparatively weak differentiation of discrete trace fossils.

414 Therefore, we strive to demonstrate the utility of the applied methods in the case
415 of modern marine sediments that are mainly retrieved from deep-marine settings
416 (Dorador et al., 2014a, b; Rodríguez-Tovar and Dorador, 2015) and ichnofacies (Dorador
417 and Rodríguez-Tovar, 2015). Depositional processes (i.e., pelagic, gravitational and
418 bottom-current) determining variations in environmental conditions (i.e., organic matter
419 deposition, oxygenation of the pore water, etc.) can be approached through deep-sea
420 ichnological research (Wetzel, 2010; Uchman and Wetzel, 2011; Wetzel and Uchman,
421 2012), and facilitated by novel applications.

422 Image processing techniques should therefore be considered as an essential tool
423 for sedimentary basin research, supported by ichnological information, and not only when
424 working with marine cores from modern deposits, but also based on outcrop studies.

425

426 **5. Conclusions**

427

428 The usefulness of Fiji and ICY methods for ichnological studies has been tested
429 and compared with high-resolution image treatment. Concretely, their efficiency in the
430 enhancing of trace fossils visibility, quantification of the bioturbation and estimation of
431 penetration depth were tested.

432 High-resolution image treatment (+ RefineEdge) is revealed as the best option to
433 increase visibility of trace fossils. However, Fiji (CLAHE) proved to be a rapid alternative
434 for preliminary analysis of cores when selecting the most appropriate segments in the
435 initial stages of research.

436 Regarding the quantification of the bioturbation, the Magic Wand Method (+
437 RefineEdge) provides good results regardless of image contrast, allowing for
438 quantification of the area occupied by each ichnotaxon, the whole icnocoenosis, or the
439 complete ichnofabric. Notwithstanding, Fiji and ICY (+ Fiji) stand as faster alternatives
440 to quantify the whole of the bioturbated surface, especially recommended in early
441 research stages.

442 Quantitative pixel analysis and IP-ICY are useful for estimating penetration depth,
443 but the semi-automatic character of IP-ICY favors speedy calculation.

444 Therefore, use of the newly tested techniques (Fiji and ICY) is highly
445 recommended during early stages of research as an initial approach or to filter the
446 adequate representative samples. The great potential of these techniques should be further
447 explored in the realms of ichnological analysis, and particularly for sedimentary basin

448 research, as ichnological information reported thus far is well supported and quite
449 promising.

450

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452

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464

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603

604 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

605

606 **Fig. 1.** Example of Fiji treatment stages to enhance trace fossil visualization (A) and
607 quantify the bioturbated surface (B). Scale bars = 1 cm.

608 **Fig. 2.** Example of ICY treatment stages to enhance trace fossil visualization (A) and
609 quantify the bioturbated surface (B). Note that bioturbation is assigned to white pixels
610 and the last stages of filtering and inversion are assisted by Fiji. Scale bars = 1 cm.

611 **Fig. 3.** Example of high-resolution image treatment application to enhance trace fossil
612 visibility by the modification of image adjustments (A) and for quantification of
613 bioturbated surface (B). SPSM, Similar Pixel Selection Method; MWM, Magic Wand
614 Method; CRSM, Color Range Selection Method. Scale bars = 1 cm.

615 **Fig. 4.** Original images and obtained results after application of high-resolution image
616 treatment, CLAHE extension by Fiji, and the adaptive histogram by ICY on high, medium

617 and low contrast samples. Scale bars = 1cm. *Pl*, *Planolites*; *Th*, *Thalassinoides*; *Ch*,
618 *Chondrites*.

619 **Fig. 5.** Quantification of percentage of bioturbated surface by different methods of high-
620 resolution image treatment, Fiji and ICY software. CRSM, Color Range Selection
621 Method; MWM, Magic Wand Method; SPSM, Similar Pixel Selection Method. Scale
622 bars = 1cm.

623 **Fig. 6.** Penetration depth of trace fossils obtained with quantitative pixel analysis (left)
624 and IP-ICY (right) methodology in high (A) and low (B) contrast core examples. Note:
625 left scale in cm.

626

627 **TABLE CAPTION**

628 **Table 1.** Summary of strengths and weaknesses of each methodology depending on the
629 purpose.

630

A

Enhancing trace fossils visibility

Original

Treated by Fiji (CLAHE)

B

Quantification

Binary

Filtered

Original image

High-resolution image treatment

Fiji (CLAHE)

Adaptive histogram by ICY

High contrast

Medium contrast

Low contrast

Methods	Enhancing visibility of trace fossils	Quantification of bioturbated surface	Estimation of penetration depth
High-resolution image treatment (+ RefineEdge)	Good results for any image (high to low contrast), based on the modification of three image adjustments (<i>levels, brightness and vibrance</i>). Application of different colors facilitates ichnotaxonomy.	CRSM and MWM provide reasonable values for high and medium contrast images. MWM is also useful in low contrast images, but it is time-consuming. Application of different colors allows detailed quantification.	Good estimation, but time-consuming.
Fiji	It provides good results for any image in a rapid way. Binary character makes ichnotaxonomical differentiation difficult.	Good for high and low contrast images, but after complex filtering. Only for quantification of total bioturbated surface.	Not possible.
ICY	Successful for high contrast images. Binary character makes ichnotaxonomical differentiation difficult.	Good for high and medium contrast images, but it requires complex filtering. Note that the last stages have to be conducted with Fiji. Only for quantification of total bioturbated surface.	Good estimation in a very rapid way. Facilitates differentiation between specimens.